

USING THE COOPERATIVE LEARNING FOR TEACHING IDIOMS ON FRENCH FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The objective of this study is to detect the effect of using cooperative learning for teaching idioms to first grade students, learning French as a foreign language. The study was carried out on two groups – experimental group and control group – during the academic year of 2017-2018 in the lesson “Reading in French”. The lesson was taught using traditional teaching methods with the control group, while using Jigsaw-II technique with the experimental group. According to the findings obtained from this research, the experimental group students, on whom the Jigsaw-II technique was applied, became more successful within the scope of learning idioms in French language.

Keywords: cooperative learning, Jigsaw-II technique, reading in a foreign language, learning French idioms, reading in French

1. Introduction

In today’s educational system, the students are expected to be more active in the class while learning a foreign language, unlike traditional teaching methods. Therefore, it has become more important for the students, learning a foreign language, to stop remaining passive, who only listen to their teachers and answer the questions, but rather, to become an individual, interacting with both their friends and teachers in the class, as well as exchanging information, and achieving autonomous learning. In education of students with such characteristics, it is of vital importance to select the teaching methods that comply with the teachers, students and course content (Ünsal & Moğol, 2004).

It was set forth in many studies that the learning methods of the students in classroom environment, along with having unique personal characteristics, may differ from each other. At that rate, teachers may confront with a number of challenges in

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educating the students with unique characteristics for developing foreign language and communication skills. For this reason, the need for teaching methods, which provide the opportunity to eliminate or minimize the challenges that may occur due to the unique characteristics of these students, in teaching foreign language emerges, while the question “How do students learn?” (Abrami, 1996) gains more importance.

In this case, the teachers are expected to create a learning environment for students to make them act more actively in the class, upskilling their language skills, along with communication and social skills, and also studying & learning with their friends.

One of the teaching methods for ensuring the students with interests, skill levels, motivation and thinking style that are different from each other, to gather and participate actively in the in-class activities, is Cooperate Learning Method.

2. Cooperative Learning Method

Cooperative learning is an interactive and structured learning method comprising students with different skills and characteristics supporting and helping each other, in order to make a common cause within each other (Baudrit, 2005). In other words; *“cooperative is working together to accomplish shared goals. Within cooperative situations, individuals seek outcomes beneficial to themselves and all other group members. Cooperative learning is the instructional use of small groups through which students work together to maximize their own and each other’s learning. It may be contrasted with competitive learning in which students work against each other to achieve an academic goal such as a grade of «A»”* (Richards & Rogers, 2001, as cited in Boussiada, 2010).

As can be understood from this statement, students learn by working in small groups, being aware of their own responsibilities in a lesson, which is organized based on cooperative learning method.

There are more and more researches substantiating opinion that CL improves not only comprehension (reading and listening) and cognition but also communication skills and enhance the quality of interaction with other participants of learning processes (Stepanoviene, 2013). In every step of the education life from the primary school to college, cooperative learning method is applicable. As stated by Nevin et al. (1998), students in higher education become more successful thanks to cooperative learning, while acquiring the skills on cooperative studying, and having more fun while learning. For this method to be carried out successfully in a class environment, it is necessary for the teacher to properly structure the lesson activities. Participation of each member is achievable solely with this method (Mallard, 2003). Otherwise, it would simple be recognized as a simple group study.

The table below shows the differences between cooperative learning method and traditional learning methods. It can be seen that the cooperative learning method has several characteristics in common with the communicational method (Zang, 2010). They both highlight to the interaction and communication between students and students

and teachers, take teachers' role as guider, facilitator, and negotiator, and stress the autonomy and centrality of the students in classroom (ibid, 2010).

Table 1: Comparison of cooperative language learning method and traditional language learning methods

	Traditional language teaching	Cooperative language learning
Independence	None or negative	Positive
Learner roles	Passive receiver and performer	Active participator, autonomous learners
Teacher roles	The center of the classroom, Controller of teaching pace and direction, judge of students' right or wrong, the major source of assistance, feedback, reinforcement and support.	Organizer and counselor of group work, facilitator of the communication tasks, intervener to teach collaborative skills.
Materials	Complete set of materials for each student.	Materials are arranged according to purpose of lesson. Usually one group shares a complete set of materials.
Types of activities	Knowledge recall and review, phrasal or sentence pattern practice, role play, translation, listening etc.	Any instructional activity, mainly group work to engage learners in communication, involving processes like information sharing, negotiation of meaning and interaction.
Interaction	Some talking among students, mainly teacher-student interaction	Intense interaction among students, a few teacher-student interaction
Room arrangement	Separate desks or students placed in pairs.	Collaborative small groups
Student expectations	Take a major part in evaluating own progress and the quality of own efforts toward learning. Be a winner or loser.	All members in some way contribute to success of group. The one who makes progress is the winner.
Teacher-student relationship	Superior-inferior or equal	Cooperating and equal

They both focus on the interaction and communication between students and students and teachers, taking teachers' role as guider, facilitator, and negotiator, and stress the autonomy and centrality of the students in classroom (ibid, 2010).

However, not every small group study in a classroom is recognized as cooperative learning method. For a group study to be recognized as cooperative learning method, the following elements are deemed required:

- **Positive Interdependence:** The basis of cooperative learning comprises of ensuring the developing & sustaining of positive interdependence among the group members. Therefore, positive interdependence is one of the most important principles of cooperative learning. Positive interdependence emerges when group members feel that what helps one member, helps all and what hurts one member, hurts all (Richards & Rogers, 2001). In this case, the students need each other to achieve the common target. With positive interdependence, the group members learn how to contribute in their efforts, teach each other and trust in their on their own capacities (Clarke et al., 1992). According to Howden

and Kopiec (2002), positive interdependence is the key to productivity, motivation and group harmony. The positive interdependence among the members in a classroom environment can be ensured with the target set, duties, rewards, along with various roles assigned to the group members and the lesson material used (Lopriore, 1999).

- **Face-to-face Interaction:** Face-to-face interaction is frequently seen in cooperative learning. Notwithstanding that it is the student-teacher interaction, which is frequently seen in traditional classroom environments, student-student interaction is also seen, along with student-teacher interaction, in classroom environments where cooperative learning method is applied (Jacob et al. 2002). The students help each other learn in a group study within the scope of cooperative learning, while exchanging ideas, sharing lesson materials, thus bringing in a mutual product (Gillies & Ashman, 2003). Hence, face-to-face interaction is seen between students within the entire process.
- **Individual Accountability:** Individual accountability is one of the fundamental elements of cooperative learning method, which ensures the group studies to be maintained more properly and prevents conflict of duties. Each and every student in the group is responsible for fulfilling his/her own duty, personal learning and learning of his/her friends from the group, as well (Lopriore, 1999). *“Individual accountability exists when the performance of each individual is assessed and the results are given back to the group and the individual in order to ascertain who needs more assistance, support, and encouragement in learning. The purpose of cooperative learning groups is to make each member a stronger individual in his or her right”* (Puspita, 2018). Individual accountability can be achieved with various roles assigned to the students, as follows: (keansburg.k12.nj.us):
 - *“Organizer (provides the group with the overall process structure),*
 - *Recorder (writes down important information),*
 - *Encourager (models and reinforces appropriate social skills),*
 - *Summarizer (restates the team’s conclusions or answers,*
 - *Spokesperson (represents the group and presents group work to rest of the class),*
 - *Timekeeper (keeps group on task and on time)”*
- **Social Skills:** Gaining social skills, which are ignored in traditional teaching methods, are frequently seen in cooperative learning method. Respecting each other and learning to get along are the most important matters in cooperative learning groups (Jordan & Le Métails, 1997). The continuity of groups can only be achieved by this way. Students gain certain fundamental social skills like listening to each other, exchanging ideas, encouraging each other, communicating and cooperating in the group study. (Abrami et al. 1996). However, social skills for effective cooperative work do not magically appear when cooperative lessons are employed. Instead, social skills are to be taught to students as purposefully and precisely as academic skills (Puspita, 2018).

- **Use of Reward:** According to Burton et al. (2003), reward refers to anything that promotes a behavior being repeated in the future. Therefore, a reward is an incentive that induces learners' engagement in a particular task. It can take the form of monetary, symbolic reward, or feedback. According to Slavin (1990) and Johnson (1981), reward is as important as individual accountability and assessment of success in cooperative learning, and also it ensures the success levels of students to be increased, while changing the classroom atmosphere positively (Bilgin & Geban, 2004). A mutual reward to be granted to the whole group will ensure the students to be aware of their own success and to do the best they can for clearing up the problems.

2. Historical Development of Cooperative Learning

In the historical process of language learning from past to date, researchers have kept seeking for an effective way to teach a foreign language. For more than hundred years, the shift within language teaching profession emphasized the role of the learner in the process of learning and teaching. As a result, in recent years, some significant development began to take place and effective cooperative learning comes to the scene (Boussiada, 2010).

“The Roman philosopher, Seneca advocated cooperative learning through such statements as, ‘Qui Docet Discet’ (when you teach, you learn twice). Johann Amos Comenius (1592-1679) believed that students would benefit both by teaching and being taught by other students. In the late 1700s Joseph Lancaster and Andrew Bell made extensive use of cooperative learning groups in England, and the idea was brought to America when a Lancastrian school was opened in New York City in 1806” (Johnson & Johnson, 1989).

Therefore, the history of cooperative learning methods goes back to more than one hundred years, having a deeper root than 20th century (Slavin, 1995). Mentioning the closest period to date, cooperative language learning is mainly based on the works of Jean Piaget's (1965) and Lev Vygotsky's (1962) developmental theories which emphasize the importance of discussion and joint problem solving among peers. Both of them stress the role of social interaction in learning (Boussiada, 2010). Cooperative learning method has been produced as the product of a number of experimental and theoretical researches, which are based on certain theories.

3. Theoretical Bases of Cooperative Learning

3.1. Social Interdependence Theory

This theory is based on the harmony and interdependence of the group members with each other, which is considered as a critical factor, affecting the group success. According to Johnson and Johnson (2009), social interdependence exists when the

outcomes of individuals are affected by their own and others' actions. There are two types of social interdependence: positive (when the actions of individuals promote the achievement of joint goals) and negative (when the actions of individuals obstruct the achievement of each other's goals). Additionally, social interdependence leads to interaction among students, as well. Therefore, it is not possible to mention interaction of any kind, where there is no interdependence among the group members, and where the individuals study as independent from each other (Saban, 2001).

According to the theorists defending the social interdependence theory, cooperation (helping each other) is not possible unless the students care about their groups. Constituting positive interdependence among the students can be achieved by assigning different tasks to each of them, holding them liable for their own material, as well as creating up of the lesson material by the teacher in a manner that creates the interdependence among students.

According to the Russian psychologist L. S. Vygotsky, the most fundamental matter in the student's improvement is to have a social environment, where he/she can interact with others (Oortwijn, Boekaerts & Vedder, 2008). Therefore, cooperative learning method encourage the students to be in interaction with the group members, as well as ensuring them to learn from each other, by providing them with the opportunity to study in groups.

3.2. Motivational Learning Theory

Learning methods, which are applied in classroom environments, can be summarized under three groups. These are competitive, individuative and cooperative learning methods. *"Slavin (1996) criticizes the competitive grading structure of the traditional classroom for creating opportunities to demonstrate superiority over one's peers, which can result in a deleterious effect on academic effort. Therefore, motivational theories have built models of incentive structures which incorporate variables of both one's own achievement and peers' attainment into CL methods"* (Lin, 2015).

Some of the theorist, supporting this theory, underline that reinforcement and reward are of great importance in learning. Based on this idea, learning-based activities are to be supported with continuous external rewards (Johnson & Johnson, 1994). According to Dörnyei (2001 cited in Lin, 2015), further comments that, in a CL directed class, learners work with their peers so that responsibility for the learning outcomes is shared. Students are equally rewarded, which is in contrast to a competitive structure in which only the best learner in the class is praised.

3.3. Cognitive Development Theory

Cognitive development theory is based on the studies by Piaget and Vygotsky. Knowledge is constructed with cooperative efforts; group members share information and ideas with each other, discovering the weaknesses in their logical bases, correcting each other, as well as reconstructing their personal understandings based on their mutual understanding (Johnson and Johnson, 1992, as cited in Aslandağ Soylu, 2008). *"To Jean Piaget (1950, as cited in Johnson& Johnson 2015), cooperation is striving to attain*

common goals while coordinating one's own feelings and perspective with a consciousness of others' feelings and perspective". In other words, "cooperation in the Piagetian tradition is aimed at increasing a person's intellectual development by forcing him or her to reach consensus with others who hold opposing points of view about the answer to the problem" (Johnson & Johnson, 2015).

4. Contributions of Cooperative Learning Method to Students in Learning a Foreign Language

It was set forth in many studies that cooperative learning method is an effective way for improving the motivation, productivity and success level of students in learning a foreign language. Hence, we can summarize the contributions of this method to students as follows: (i) encouraging the student to learning and academic success, (ii). increasing the satisfaction level of students in the learning process, (iii) helping students improve their verbal communication skills, (iv) improving the social skills and self-respect of students (Marzano, Pickering & Pollock, 2001).

To Zang (2010), the contributions of cooperative learning method can be summarized as follows:

- *"Providing the chances of input and output. Cooperative language learning creates natural, interactive contexts, where students listen to each other, ask question, and clarify issues. Group interaction assists learners in negotiating for more comprehensible input and in modifying their output to make it more comprehensible to others.*
- *Creating effective climate. Cooperative learning offers a relaxed climate in the classroom, while it also increases student motivation. Therefore, more participation will inevitably increase learner's self-confidence and self-esteem.*
- *Increasing a variety of language functions. Cooperative language learning allows learners more chances to produce language in a functional manner. In traditional classroom, discourse is usually initiated by the teacher in an artificial setting, but cooperative learning can be used to create a mimic real-life social settings in which language is normally used.*
- *Fostering learner responsibility and independence. Cooperative learning make each student a stronger individual through doing work cooperatively. Cooperative learning, therefore, emphasizes individual accountability".*

5. Techniques in Cooperative Learning Method

Cooperative learning method comprises a great number of teaching techniques, which can be selected and used by the teachers based on their pedagogical needs. Following are some of the techniques and short descriptions, which are frequently used in teaching environments:

5.1. Learning Together (LT)

The techniques, as developed by Johnson and Johnson in 1970s, focused on teaching the students via positive interaction techniques, rather than making them learn the lesson material and develop cognitive skills (Abrami et al. 1996). In this technique, the students study in small heterogeneous groups in order to create a group project. The leading concept under this instruction is 'interdependence' (Boussiada, 2010).

The most significant characteristics of this technique is the sharing of a common target, ideas and materials, sharing of tasks and rewarding the groups. During the first applications to put out a single product working in groups, sharing ideas and materials, asking each other their questions before teacher have supplied to be rewarded (Açıkgöz 2003 as cited in Gökkurt et al. 2012).

5.2 Jigsaw I

Jigsaw I was developed by Elliot Aronson in order to minimize the differences of students coming from different ethnic origins. In the advancing years, this technique started to be used as a complementary element in teaching and was accepted to ensure that the students develop positive attitudes against the school and themselves within the group studies (Aronson, 1997).

In this technique, the students study in two different groups: the home team group and expert group. The lesson material to be learned is divided into different sections, as equal to the number of students, and in a manner complementing each other in this technique (Abrami et al. 1996). Each team is given a unit (subject) and the members of the teams select one of the unit parts (sub-topics). Students, selecting the same sub-topic in all teams, are gathered within the expert group, to study on the subject and discuss with each other. Then, they return to their original teams and inform their team-mates by lecturing on the respective topic (Akyol, 2018).

Figure 1: The "Jigsaw" Technique

5.3. Jigsaw II

Jigsaw II was developed by Slavin, by means of making certain changes on Jigsaw I technique, as developed by Aronson. These two techniques have both common and different characteristics (Slavin, 1991):

- Students in Jigsaw I, read their chapters personally, unlike their friends in the group.
- The most challenging characteristic of Jigsaw I is the requirement that each and every lesson material, to be given to the group members, must be originally prepared and comprehensible.
- The advantage of Jigsaw II is that the group members are given the opportunity to read the entire material all together.

The phases that are to be followed in Jigsaw II, are as follows (Slavin 1994):

- **Preparing the lesson material:** The teacher should prefer short texts for activities to be conducted within the classroom.
- **Distributing the students to home team groups:** Heterogenous groups, comprising of 4 or 5 students, are formed. These groups are the home team groups of the students. Each group member is assigned with a role. There is no group leader.
- **Studying process of Jigsaw groups:** The teacher shares the lesson material with the students. The students, having the same part of the material, come together to form the expert group, and study the parts, for which they are held responsible. They work all together in order to ensure that each group member understands the lesson material.
- **Home team group report:** After the students study the respective parts, they return to their original groups (home team) to teach their friends in the group what they learned. Each group member is responsible for teaching his/her own part to group members. After every group member understands the subject, they are subjected to a test (quiz) by the teacher.
- **Exam (Quiz):** Students are subjected to an individual test. This is generally a short quiz, comprising multiple-choice questions. The student with the highest score wins the first place in the group, thus being rewarded.

The following table displays how student grouping is performed in Jigsaw techniques (home team/expert team) (Jacobs, Power & Loh, 2002 as cited in Apple, 2006).

5.4. Student Teams-Achievement Divisions

STAD is a cooperative learning technique, which is used by students for achieving the shared learning target, studying in small groups of 4 to 5, with different skill levels. It was devised by Robert Slavin and his associates at Johns Hopkins University, students are assigned to four or five member learning teams that are mixed based on performance level, gender, and ethnicity (Tiantong & Teemuangsai, 2013).

Implementation of STAD is relatively easier compared to other cooperative techniques. This technique is ideal for teachers, who plan to implement cooperative

learning method for the first time in the class (Slavin, 1980). *“The teacher presents a lesson, and then students work together within their teams to make sure that all team members have mastered the lesson. Finally, all students take individual quizzes on the material, at which time they may not help one another. Students’ quiz scores are compared to their own past averages, and points are awarded on the basis of the degree to which students meet or exceed their own earlier performance”* (Tiantong & Teemuangsai, 2013).

These points are then summed to obtain team scores. Some teachers provide certain kinds of recognition or reward to students on ‘Great team’ or ‘Super team’ (Slavin 1995).

5.5. Teams-Games-Tournaments

This technique was developed by Devries, Edwards and Slavin. It is conditioned by the students’ active involvement in weekly tournaments or games. Students work in small groups to learn the assigned material. Competition is created between students who have the same level but placed in other groups. Rewards are afforded to high performing teams (Bouguerne, 2011). The students compete with the students from other groups, instead of being subjected to a quiz as applied in STAD, in this technique, and they support their teams with the scores they obtained at the end of the competition (Yağcı, Kaptı & Beyaztaş, 2012).

5.6. Group Investigation

Group investigation technique was developed by John Dewey, which was subjected to certain revisions by Shlomo and Yael Sharan, afterwards. In this method, group composition is based on students’ interest, and it is heterogeneous. Students form their own two-to-six groups (Boussiada, 2010).

As can be clearly understood from the name, itself, the students carry out investigations from certain resources inside and outside the classroom. In this technique, the students are subjected to continuous assessment. *“In group investigation, groups choose topics from a unit studied by the entire class. A central role to group investigation is students’ cooperative planning of the learning task. Each group members takes part in determining what they want to investigate in order to solve the problem, which resources they need, which will do what and how they will present their project to the class as a whole. Usually there is a division in the group that enhances positive interdependence”* (ibid, 2010).

Despite having limited number of studies in the use of cooperative learning in teaching the idioms to the students, learning French as a foreign language, which has led to positive outputs in terms of students’ success levels, and which is researched in many foreign and national studies on education, it was deemed as a must for us to carry out this study. It was aimed at answering the following questions within the scope of this research:

1. What is the effect of cooperative learning in teaching idioms in French language on the students success?

1.1. Does it lead to a significant difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental groups to use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?

1.2. Is there a significant difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental groups, on which Jigsaw-II technique is used in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?

1.3. Does it lead to a significant difference in terms of gender to use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?

1.4. Is there a significant different in the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental group and the control group?

6. Method

This research is a quantitative study, carried out on two groups (experimental group and control group). The preliminary – final test control group model was used in the research. In this model, there are two objectively-assigned groups. One of them is the experimental group, and the other one is the control group. The measurements are made before and after the experiment in both groups. The symbolical image of the model is as follows (Karasar, 1995):

Figure 2: Preliminary - final test control group model

Additionally, the time series research design was used in order to detect the effect of using Jigsaw-II technique on students while teaching the idioms in French as a foreign language on a weekly basis, within the scope of the experimental group. In this model, there is a single randomly-assigned group. Monitoring method and independent variable (x) are subjected to periodic measurements. (Karasar, 1995)

Time series research design is one of the most ideal research models, which can be used by the researcher having to fulfill the observation with a number of preliminary and final tests within a certain period of time (Cresswell, 2005). The flow chart, as suggested by Cresswell (2005) for the time series research design is as follows:

The flow chart of this research, as per the time series research design, is as follows:

Time: 6 weeks →

Selecting the members of the experimental group	Preliminary Test	Use of Jigsaw-II technique	Quiz 1	Use of Jigsaw-II technique	Quiz 2	Use of Jigsaw-II technique	...	Quiz 6	Final test
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6.1. Participants

16 of the students, comprising the research group of the study, were in the experimental group, while 15 of them were in the control group. The research was carried out in French Reading – II, as a compulsory lesson, which was being lectured for three hours weekly, in the 2017-2018 academic year’s spring term. 31 students, participating in the research (Experimental group + control group) were studying in the first grade in Anadolu University, Faculty of Education, Department of French Teaching, and their foreign language skill level was confirmed to be B1 (1 year of preparation + undergraduate education).

6.2. Data Collection

Within the framework of this research, a preliminary test was applied on the experimental and control groups before the application process, in order to measure their knowledge levels on idioms in French as a foreign language (Quiz on French Idioms). The Quiz on French Idioms, as prepared by the researcher, comprises of 35 questions, which was controlled by two academic members, who were experts in their fields. The idioms, which are used in daily-life in France and which can be seen by students in their text books, were utilized while preparing the Quiz on French Idioms.

During the spring semester, the lesson was lectured for 6 weeks with both groups in teaching idioms. While the traditional teaching methods were followed in the control group, the Jigsaw-II method was used, as a technique in Cooperative Learning Method.

The idioms, which were planned to be taught, were given to the students in reading texts. The reading texts, which involves the idioms asked within the preliminary and final tests and used in the lesson, were prepared by the researchers with the help of various dissertations, books and internet resources. The same texts were used in both groups; however, the texts were regulated as per the Jigsaw-II technique for the experimental group. In addition to teaching idioms, the texts were supplemented with a number of reading-comprehension questions in order not to neglect these activities. The texts used in the control group were not subjected to any change in terms of its form.

The students in the experimental group were subjected to Quizzes at the end of every lesson for 6 weeks. These quizzes comprise of the idioms that were taught in the lesson and 10 multiple-choice questions.

Following a 6-weeks of application process with both groups, the French Idiom Test, which was used as preliminary test, was used as the final test this time.

6.3. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The question no 1.1 of this research is as follows: *Does it lead to a significant difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental groups to use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?* The paired student t-test was carried out to answer this question. For controlling the normal distribution, first the skewness and kurtosis values were checked. According to this, it was noted that the skewness and kurtosis values of preliminary scores ($skewness_{prel.test} = -.740$ and $kurtosis_{prel.test} = .997$) and the final test scores from the same test ($skewness_{finaltest} = -.937$ and $kurtosis_{finaltest} = -.151$) were within the range of -1 to +1. The skewness and kurtosis values of the difference scores in two related measuring-set must be checked in order to control the normal distribution in the paired student t-Test (Büyüköztürk, 2003). Accordingly, it was noted that the skewness and kurtosis values of the score differences ($skewness_{diff} = -.260$ ve $kurtosis_{diff} = .579$) were within the range -1 to +1. To Huck (2012), in a normal distribution, the skewness and kurtosis values must be within the range -1 to +1. It was confirmed that three values, as above stated, meet this requirement. In addition to these values, Shapiro-Wilk test results were examined. Shapiro-Wilk test is used when the sample size is low ($n < 50$). It was seen that the preliminary test results [$D(16) = .958$, $p = .627$] and score difference results [$D(16) = .985$, $p = .992$] displayed a normal distribution, while the final test results [$D(16) = .829$, $p = .007$] did not (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965). In addition to this, Çokluk, Şekercioğlu and Büyüköztürk (2010) suggest that determining the normal distribution should not be solely based on a single condition. According to this theory, it is recognized to be useful to include more than one situation. In this context, histogram, Q-Q and detrended Q-Q graphics were used. According to these graphics, the variables were detected to display normal distribution. The paired student t-Test results on whether there is a significant difference between the scores of the students on recognizing the French idioms, studying in the Department of French Teaching, before and after the implementation process.

Table 2: t-Test results for scores on recognizing the French idioms

Group	$\bar{x}$	Ss	t	Sd	p<
Preliminary-final test	-54.500	13,059	-16.694	15	.001

The difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the 1st grade students on French Idioms, who study in the department of French Teaching, are statistically significant [$t(15) = -16.694$, $p < .001$]. Considering the average scores, it can be seen that the final-test scores are higher than the preliminary test scores ($\bar{x}_{finaltest} > \bar{x}_{prel.test}$). This shows that the success levels of students were improved after the implementation.

The column chart, as below stated, shows that the success levels of students were improved after the implementation in learning French Idioms, by the use of Jigsaw-II technique on experimental group students.

Graphic 1: Preliminary and final test scores of the experimental group students

The question no.: 1.2 of the research is as follows: *Is there a significant difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental groups, on which Jigsaw-II technique is used in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?*

For finding the answer to this question, single-factorial ANOVA was used for repeated measurements in order to analyze the differences within the scope of preliminary-test, quiz and final-test scores of the students. This analysis type is utilized in order to analyze the measurements of the same group for a single dependent variable within three or more different periods (Akbulut, 2010). For this analysis to be carried out, the dependent variable must be continuous; the scores of dependent variable must display normal distribution and sphericity assumptions must be available. The preliminary test, quiz and final-test scores, as dependent variable, are continuous. Normal distribution of the scores was ensured, which was the second condition. According to this, it was confirmed that the skewness and kurtosis values of the dependent variables were between the range of -2 to +2, which is the acceptable range (George & Mallery, 2010). The sphericity, as the final assumption, was not fulfilled. But, this condition cannot be met in general (Akbulut, 2010). In this case, the Greenhouse-Geisser order is read within the Tests of Within-Subjects Effects table. These values can be seen in Table-3.

Table 3: Results for the difference between the preliminary test, quizzes and final test

Variance Resource	KT	Sd	KO	F	p	η^2	Power
Measurement	36623.429	3.157	11599.332	95.973	0.000	0.865	1.000
Error	5724.000	47.361	120.860				

Considering the information stated in Table-6, it was noted that the difference between the measurements was significant (Wilk's Lambda: .025; $p < .001$; $\eta^2 = .865$; Power = 1.000). In addition to this, it can be said that a high amount of influence quantity and power is present. For calculating the influence quantity indicates low influence, where the et square value is between .01-.06; medium between .06-.14 and high between .14 and over (Huck, 2012). On the other hand, for identifying the tests, in which this

significant difference is present, the Pairwise Comparison table was analyzed. According to this table, the tests with significant differences are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Table indicating the significant differences between the tests

(I) Tests	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b		
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Prel-Test	Quiz1	-30,250*	3,986	,000	-44,789	-15,711
	Quiz2	-36,500*	2,596	,000	-45,971	-27,029
	Quiz3	-45,875*	4,398	,000	-61,917	-29,833
	Quiz4	-49,625*	3,361	,000	-61,886	-37,364
	Quiz5	-55,875*	3,001	,000	-66,823	-44,927
Quiz1	Final-Test	-54,500*	3,265	,000	-66,409	-42,591
	Quiz3	-15,625*	3,158	,004	-27,145	-4,105
	Quiz4	-19,375*	2,657	,000	-29,065	-9,685
	Quiz5	-25,625*	2,577	,000	-35,025	-16,225
	Final-Test	-24,250*	2,175	,000	-32,183	-16,317
Quiz2	Quiz4	-13,125*	2,536	,002	-22,376	-3,874
	Quiz5	-19,375*	1,930	,000	-26,414	-12,336
Quiz4	Final-Test	-18,000*	1,871	,000	-24,824	-11,176
	Quiz5	-6,250*	1,548	,023	-11,896	-,604

Considering the Table 4, the preliminary-test average score ($\bar{x}=41.00$) is lower than Quiz 1 ($\bar{x}=71.25$). It can also be seen that the preliminary test score is similarly lower than Quiz 2 ($\bar{x}=73.86$), Quiz 3 ($\bar{x}=86.88$), Quiz 4 ($\bar{x}=90.63$), Quiz 5 ($\bar{x}=96.88$) and final test average scores ($\bar{x}=95.50$).

The average score from Quiz I ($\bar{x}=71.25$) was found to be lower than Quiz 3 ($\bar{x}=86.88$), Quiz 4 ($\bar{x}=90.63$), Quiz 5 ($\bar{x}=96.88$) and final test average score ($\bar{x}=95.50$), on the other hand, Quiz 2 average test score was lower than Quiz 4 ($\bar{x}=90.63$) and Quiz 5 ($\bar{x}=96.88$), as the last 2 quizzes, and final-test average score ($\bar{x}=95.50$).

Lastly, the average scores from Quiz 5, as the last test ($\bar{x}=96.88$) was found to be higher than Quiz 4 average score ($\bar{x}=90.63$). Examining the above stated data, it can be said that the students' success levels have increased in time compared to their levels before the implementation.

The question no.: 1.3. of the research is as follows: *Does it lead to a significant difference in terms of gender to use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?* Unpaired t-Test was applied for answering this question. For carrying out this test, the sample size must be at least 30 (Chakravarti, Laha & Roy, 1967). It was noted that the requirement, within the scope of sample size, was not met. However, normal distributions are required to be checked in order to put t-Test into practice (Akbulut, 2010). According to the controls in this context, it was detected that the final-test scores of the students (skewness_{final-test}= .571 and kurtosis_{final-test}= -1.934), along with

their genders ($skewness_{gender} = -.937$ and $kurtosis_{gender} = -.151$) were within the range of -2 to +2 (Blest, 2003). Additionally, more than one factor is to be utilized for specifying the normal distribution (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu & Büyüköztürk, 2010). Therefore, histogram and quarter graphics were examined, as well. Following these reviews, it was detected that both variables displayed normal distribution. Unpaired t-Test result, concerning whether the final test scores display a significant difference in terms of gender, can be found in Table 5.

Table 5: t-Test results for final-test scores on the use of jigsaw-II technique

Gender	n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	t	Sd	p
Female	10	95.70	4.968			
Male	6	95.17	5.231	204	14	.841

The difference within the scope of gender, in the use of Jigsaw-II technique while teaching the French idioms to students studying in the department of French Teaching, is not statistically significant [$t(14) = .204, p = .841$].

The question no.: 1.4. of the research, which is: *Is there a significant different in the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental group and the control group?* is aimed at analyzing whether the preliminary and final test scores display a significant difference between the experimental group and control group. In this context, unpaired t-Test was engaged for two situations. First, it was examined whether there was a difference between the experimental group and control group in terms of preliminary test results. In this context, the preliminary test scores of the participants, along with the normal distribution of experimental & control groups, were controlled. According to this, it was noted that the preliminary test scores of the students ($skewness_{prel.test} = -.708$ and $kurtosis_{prel.test} = .803$) were within the range of -1 to +1. The skewness value of the group variable is within this range, as well ($skewness_{group} = .068$). However, the kurtosis value is not within this range ($kurtosis_{group} = -2.138$). In addition to these values, the results of Shapiro-Wilk test were examined. Shapiro-Wilk test is carried out, where the sample size is low ($n < 50$). It was detected that the preliminary test scores displayed a normal distribution [$D(31) = .938, p = .072$] according to this test Shapiro & Wilk 1965). But, the group variable did not display the same [$D(31) = .638, p < .001$]. According to Çokluk, Şekercioğlu and Büyüköztürk (2010), more than one value is to be taken into consideration for normal distribution. Therefore, the histogram and quarter graphics were identified. Unpaired t-Test results, concerning whether the preliminary test scores displayed a significant difference in terms of the groups, can be seen in Table-6.

Table 6: t-Test results of preliminary test scores in terms of groups

Group	n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	t	Sd	p
Experimental	16	41.00	9.859			
Control	15	41.13	6.865	-.043	29	.966

The difference in the preliminary test scores between Jigsaw-II technique and traditional method in teaching French idioms to the students, studying in the Department of French Teaching, is not statistically significant [$t(29) = -.043, p = .966$].

Unpaired t-Test was used for detecting whether there was a significant difference in the final-test scores of the experimental and control groups. For this test to be carried out, the final test, experimental & control groups are required to display a normal distribution. In this context, the skewness and kurtosis values of the relevant variables were examined. According to this, it was detected that the final-test scores of the students (skewness_{finaltest} = -.337 and kurtosis_{finaltest} = -1.412) were within the range of -2 to +2. The skewness value of the group variable is within this range, as well (skewness_{group} = .068). However, the kurtosis value is not within this range (kurtosis_{group} = -2.138). In addition to these values, the results of Shapiro-Wilk test were examined. It was detected that the final-test scores [$D(31) = .938, p = .072$] and the group variable [$D(31) = .638, p < .001$] displayed a normal distribution according to this test (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965). But according to Çokluk, Şekercioğlu & Büyüköztürk (2010), more than one value is to be taken into consideration for normal distribution. Therefore, the histogram and quarter graphics were identified. In this context, both variables were found to have displayed normal distribution. Unpaired t-Test results, concerning whether the final test scores displayed a significant difference in terms of the groups, can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7: t-Test results for final test scores in terms of groups

Group	n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	t	Sd	p
Experimental	16	95.50	4.899			
Control	15	68.73	6.940	10.429	29	p<.001

The difference in the final test scores between Jigsaw-II technique and traditional method in teaching French idioms to the students, studying in the Department of French Teaching, is statistically significant [$t(29) = 10.429, p < .001$]. According to this finding, it can be said that the students, learning the French idioms with Jigsaw-II technique, were more successful compared to those learning the same through traditional learning methods.

7. Conclusion

The objective of this study is to detect the effect of using Jigsaw-II technique – as a technique in cooperative learning method, for teaching idioms to first grade students, learning French as a foreign language, thus seeking to answer the following question: *On what level does the use of Jigsaw-II affect the students' success levels in French idioms, as a foreign language?*

The research was carried out on two groups: experimental group and control group. Both groups were subjected to a preliminary test on French Idioms, for measuring the knowledge level of students with regards to French Idioms before

implementation process. Jigsaw-II techniques were used in lessons with the experimental group. Students were subjected to a quiz on an individual basis at the end of each and every lesson, after studying in groups. The lessons were lectured by the teacher in the control group with the traditional teaching methods. At the end of the research, the French Idiom test, to which the students were subjected in the beginning, was carried out on the students again as the final test.

Analyzing the data for answering the first sub-question, which goes as *“Does it lead to a significant difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental groups to use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?”*, it was noted that the difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the students were statistically significant. This shows that the students were more successful in the test after the implementation process, and that Jigsaw-II technique contributes positively in the students’ success levels, in teaching a foreign language.

Analyzing the data for answering the second sub-question, which goes as *“Is there a significant difference between the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental groups, on which Jigsaw-II technique is used in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?”*, it was said that the students’ success levels were relatively higher compared to the levels before implementation process. This can be interpreted as that Jigsaw-II technique leads to a gradual increase in the students’ success levels, while teaching idioms in a foreign language.

Analyzing the data for answering the third sub-question, which goes as *“Does it lead to a significant difference in terms of gender to use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms in French as a foreign language?”*, it was detected that the use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms did not lead to a difference in terms of female and male students’ success levels, and that there was no significant difference in the students’ success levels in terms of gender.

Analyzing the data for answering the fourth sub-question, which goes as *“Is there a significant difference in the preliminary and final test scores of the experimental group and the control group?”*, it can be seen that the difference in the preliminary scores between the experimental group and the control group was not significant, meaning that the recognition levels of students from both group, with regards to the French Idioms, were similar. Examining the final-test scores of both groups, it can be seen that the experimental group, on which Jigsaw-II technique was used, was more successful compared to the students in the control group, on whom the traditional teaching methods were applied.

In conclusion, the use of Jigsaw-II technique in teaching idioms to 1st grade students, learning French as a foreign language, increased the success levels of students. However, this technique did not lead to a difference in terms of the success levels of students in teaching idioms based on gender. The success levels of female and male students were not different from each other.

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